

Extraction of Tree Level Forest Structure from Aerial Imagery and Photogrammetry Digital Surface Models

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Abstract: Forest inventory variables such as tree height, species distribution and biomass form the foundations for understanding of forest ecosystems. This paper presents an integrated workflow that combines data refinement, deep learning (DL) based Individual Tree Crown (ITC) segmentation and structural metric extraction to enhance the forest inventory process. The individual tree crown segmentation follows two steps. To close the domain gap from the publicly available RGB UAV dataset and single band panchromatic aerial imagery, we explore the possibility of involving a DL based colorization approach to generate synthetic RGB images. For tree height structure analysis, we integrate and compare canopy height observations from photogrammetry digital surface models in pixel and tree levels. In addition, we conduct an in-depth investigation to simulate the forest inventory process with various sampling plot sizes at a natural forest site.

Keywords: ITC; DSM; 3D; AI; colorization; forest inventory.

1 Introduction

Forests are crucial for global climate regulation and ecosystem functions. Understanding the 3D structural complexity of forests becomes increasingly vital for assessing their resilience due to climate change. Canopy height, crown size, and gap dynamics are among the standard forest inventory variables. Together with easier available high-resolution remote sensing data and advanced deep learning (DL) based image processing techniques, improved results are being achieved (Fassnacht et al. 2024). Accordingly, this progress further raises expectations, such as enabling individual tree level inventories using aerial data. Therefore, we aim to close this gap by investigating tree and stand-level forest 3D structures from very high-resolution aerial 2D and 3D datasets.

To enable a tree level-based analysis, Individual Tree Crown (ITC) segmentation is a fundamental step in the remote sensing image processing process. Traditional ITC segmentation methods mainly rely on the spectral and morphological features of tree crowns in 2D images (Kempf et al. 2021). DL-based ITC delineation has shown promising results on similar training and target data (Liang et al. 2026, Que et al. 2026). In practice, this remains a major limitation for forest inventory applications, due to differences in sensors, spatial resolutions, and imaging conditions. To address this issue, we investigate whether DL-based image colorization can serve as a domain-bridging step. Instead of directly applying an RGB-trained model to panchromatic

imagery, we first transform the panchromatic aerial data into synthetic RGB imagery and then perform crown delineation.

Among various 3D sensors, aerial photogrammetry is becoming the most important data source for forest inventory due to its cost-effectiveness and higher resolution (Tian et al. 2017, Liang et al. 2022). In this study, we present an in-depth investigation of height information across multiple scales, including pixel level, individual tree level, and stand level. To support this analysis, digital surface models (DSMs) derived from two different acquisition dates are selected and combined with the DL based ITC segmentation.

2 Datasets

Kranzberg is located in the north of Munich, Germany, which is a university test forest focused on tree drought stress detection. Within the framework of a Helmholtz research project-3DForestSIF, panchromatic airborne images with the resolution of 13.5 cm are captured (Tian et al. 2025).

The Digital Surface Model (DSMs) from 2016 and 2018 are generated from the multiview aerial imagery acquired with the 3K camera system (Kempf, et al. 2021). The original point cloud is calculated using semi-global matching (Tian et al. 2013, d' Angelo 2016), from which DSMs with 20 cm resolution are delivered. The canopy height model (CHM) is prepared by subtracting the digital terrain Model (DTM) from DSM, thereby representing the absolute tree height values. In this study the DTM is derived from the last-return LiDAR point cloud.

3 Method

3.1 DL based colorization and ITC delineation

In our previous study, we proposed ITCMNet, a multitask network that simultaneously performs ITC delineation and classification (Fan et al. 2026). The ITCMNet employs ConvNeXt V2 as its backbone to directly extract hierarchical spatial features from raw ultra-high-resolution RGB pixels. This framework was trained on the BAMFORESTS dataset from Germany and demonstrates strong generalization (Troles et al. 2024). Accurate individual tree detection and crown boundary delineation support more reliable tree height evaluation. In Figure 1 (a), different boundary colors show the tree species categories (such as Scots pine, European beech, and Norway spruce).

Figure 1. Bamberg data with 2 cm resolution (a), and Kranzberg panchromatic data with 13.5 cm resolution.

However, the transfer of ITC delineation models from public UAV benchmarks to our airborne imagery is rather challenging due to the clear domain gap between the source and target data. As Figure 1 shows, the BAMFORESTS benchmark consists of 2 cm RGB UAV imagery with detailed crown appearance and species-related color information, while the Kranzberg data are 13.5 cm panchromatic airborne images. Consequently, the discrepancy spans spectral information, spatial resolution, image texture, and acquisition geometry. To mitigate this mismatch, we introduced a DL based colorization step before crown delineation (Tian et al. 2025). In that previous study, Kang et al. (2023) proposed DDColor an end-to-end image colorization framework based on dual decoders. The method combines a pixel decoder for restoring spatial image structure with a query-based color decoder that learns semantic-aware color representations from multi-scale visual features. This design was proposed to improve semantic consistency, reduce color bleeding, and enhance color richness without relying on handcrafted priors. In our workflow, the panchromatic aerial imagery is first converted into synthetic RGB imagery using DDColor and then processed by the ITC delineation network. The purpose of this step is to reduce the appearance gap to the RGB source domain and improve compatibility with features learned from public UAV datasets.

3.2 From tree to stand level structural analysis

In order to estimate the individual tree heights, we combine the tree delineations derived from ITCMNet and overlay them onto the CHM model from 2016 and 2018. For a tree level-based analysis, height of each individual tree crown can be extracted by taking the maximum, mean or percentile-based height.

For the stand level-based analysis, the ITC shapefiles and corresponding CHM are used as a primary input. To simulate the forest inventory procedure, sampling plot locations are randomly selected within the study area, and circular sample plots with radii of 10 m, 15 m, and 20 m were generated to simulate the forest inventory procedure. For each plot, spatial overlap between the plot boundaries and the ITC polygons is assessed. Trees are classified as “in” if the centroid of the ITC polygon falls within the simulated forest inventory plot boundary and is used for the tree canopy structure analysis. Four structure parameters are calculated, including (i) the mean canopy height derived from the CHM within each plot, (ii) the mean height at the individual tree level, (iii) the maximum height at the pixel level, and (iv) the maximum height at the

individual tree level observed within each plot. These parameters will be composed as tree height metrics across different plot sizes for a systematic comparison.

4 Results and discussion

The proposed workflow is applied to the entire Kranzberg test region. Figure 2 shows the details of two representative subsets, one for coniferous forest and one for deciduous forest. The three columns display the original panchromatic image, AI colorized synthetic RGB image, and the ITC delineation results, respectively. As it shows, the DDColor-based preprocessing produced visually plausible synthetic RGB images from the panchromatic aerial data. In particular, crown regions, shadow transitions, and gaps between neighboring trees became more distinguishable in the colorized imagery. The resulting ITC delineation over the synthetic RGB images showed improved separation of neighboring crowns in both coniferous and deciduous stands, especially in areas where the original grayscale imagery exhibited weak local contrast. The structure of coniferous forests is relatively regular, and the tree crowns can be extracted fairly completely at different scales. In contrast, the complex structure of dense broadleaf forests makes crown segmentation challenging, with the potential for over-segmentation or under-segmentation. In particular, partially overlapping crowns remain challenging to segment. Colorization enhances the spectral separability of different tree crowns, thereby improving the segmentation results.

Figure 2. Individual tree crown segmentation overlaid on the AI colorized aerial imagery over conifer and deciduous tree strands.

With the ITC delineation results, tree level-based canopy height models are generated by calculating the mean values within each individual tree crown. Figure 3 shows the tree level-based height map from 2016 and 2018. 100 random locations from the test region are selected as the plot centers, of which 60 of them are considered valid as the generated plots have sufficient overlap with the tree canopy layers. Three different sizes of circle sampling plots are selected, which are 10, 15 and 25 meters. In each simulated inventory plot, we calculate the four variables: mean CHM height in pixel level (mean_height_all), mean

Figure 3. ITC level CHM 2016 (a) and CHM 2018 (b).

Figure 4. Plot of the extracted tree height statistics with three simulated inventory sampling plot sizes (10m, 15 m and 25m).

canopy height at individual tree level (mean_height_tree), maximum height at pixel level (max_height), and maximum height at individual tree level (max_tree). As illustrated in Figure 4, the original plots are displayed with grey dots. Outliers occur for two main reasons, inaccuracies in the original height models and changes in forest structure over time. To ensure an unbiased analysis, outliers were removed using a residual-based approach as this study focuses on a general assessment of the use of remote sensing data for forest inventory (Hawkins 1980). The selected plots are represented by black crosses. Regression lines estimated from the original plot and filtered plots are shown in red and blue, respectively. It should be noted that, in most cases, the height information extracted from 2016 and 2018 corresponds closely, which

further proves the robustness of the tree canopy height extracted from remote sensing imagery. The 'max_height' variable is more sensitive to outliers compared to other variables. However, after the filtering procedure, the regression lines show a clear improvement, especially for the case of a larger sample size ($r=25$ m).

5 Conclusions

Summarizing, our study further investigates the DL techniques to assist forest inventory process. To overcome the domain gap between the training and testing data, a DL based colorization approach is employed to generate synthetic RGB images. Subsequently, an advanced ITC segmentation approach is applied to delineate the

individual tree crown, which enables the tree level-based height analysis.

For the designed test measures, we observed that with the randomly selected test locations and different sample sizes, remote sensing data are able to deliver robust tree height values at both pixel and tree levels. These variables can be used directly to show the tree height range and height distribution. This forest height structure analysis can be further investigated in our further study. Overall, the findings highlight the potential of using remote sensing data as a reliable data source for monitoring forest structure and support its application in large-scale forest management and ecological studies.

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6 References

- d'Angelo, P. 2016. Improving semi-global matching: Cost aggregation and confidence measure. ISPRS Congress 2016, XLI-B1, The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, 299–304.
- Fan, W., Knoke, T., Troles, J., and Tian, J. 2026. Automatic tree-level based forest inventories retrieval via ultra-high resolution UAV images and deep learning. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 234, 261–274.
- Fassnacht, F. E., White, J. C., Wulder, M. A., and Næsset, E. 2024. Remote sensing in forestry: current challenges, considerations and directions. *Forestry: An International Journal of Forest Research*, 97(1), 11–37.
- Hawkins, D. M. 1980. Identification of outliers (Vol. 11). London: Chapman and Hall.
- Kang, X., Yang, T., Ouyang, W., Ren, P., Li, L., Xie, X., 2023. DDColor: Towards photo-realistic image colorization via dual decoders. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 328–338.
- Kempf, C., Tian, J., Kurz, F., D'Angelo, P., Schneider, T., and Reinartz, P. 2021. Oblique view individual tree crown delineation. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 99, 102314.
- Liang, X., Kukko, A., Balenović, I., Saarinen, N., Junttila, S., Kankare, V., and Hyyppä, J. 2022. Close-range remote sensing of forests: The state of the art, challenges, and opportunities for systems and data acquisitions. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, 10(3), 32–71.
- Liang, X., Wang, Y., Pan, J., Heiskanen, J., Wang, N., Wu, S., Gong, J. 2026. Empowering tree-scale monitoring over large areas: Individual tree delineation from high-resolution imagery. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 232, 974–999.
- Que, H., Gao, H., Shan, W., Liu, M., An, J., Deng, F., Feng, S., Yang, X., and Mu, L. 2026. FM-SAM: individual tree crown delineation and classification based on Segmentation Anything Model (SAM) and YOLOv10 in UAV imagery for forest monitoring. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 240, 111162.
- Tian, J., Reinartz, P., d'Angelo, P., and Ehlers, M. 2013. Region-based automatic building and forest change detection on Cartosat-1 stereo imagery. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 79, 226–239.
- Tian, J., Schneider, T., Straub, C., Kugler, F., and Reinartz, P. 2017. Exploring digital surface models from nine different sensors for forest monitoring and change detection. *Remote Sensing*, 9(3), 287.
- Tian, J., Panangian, D., Fan, W., Siegmann, B., and Yuan, X. 2025. Deep learning based individual tree crown delineation from panchromatic aerial imagery. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 885–892.
- Troles, J., Schmid, U., Fan, W., and Tian, J. 2024. BAMFORESTS: Bamberg benchmark forest dataset of individual tree crowns in very-high-resolution UAV images. *Remote Sensing*, 16(11), 1935.